

RESULTS OF THE ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF BIOFUELS AS ADDITIVES TO FUELS IN INTERNAL COMBUSTION ENGINES

¹Ravshan Musurmanov, ²Sobir Utaev, ³Abdugani Turaev

¹National University of Uzbekistan named after M. Ulugbek

²Karshi State University

³ National Research University Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization
Engineers

¹[0009-0007-3581-0862], ²[0000-0003-0377-8929], ³[0009-0000-3347-4219]

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The use of alternative fuels in power plants will reduce atmospheric pollution from vehicle exhaust gases and increase their fuel efficiency.

Any alternative fuel has its own disadvantages and advantages, among which the most important are:

- production costs;
- consumer availability;
- environmental impact;
- need to adapt engines to the process of feeding new fuels;
- safety of use.

Alternative fuels reduce the emission of harmful substances emitted into the atmosphere with combustion products. This applies to many alternative fuels.

The use of biological and gaseous fuels reduces emissions of hydrocarbons, CO and nitrogen oxides.

As for fuel consumption, when using alcohols it increases, and when using gaseous fuels, fuel consumption decreases.

Methanol is a very efficient fuel for positive ignition engines due to its high octane number. Methanol can be used as a standalone fuel or as an additive to petroleum fuels.

In all cases, its use allows to reduce the toxicity of engine exhaust gases. There are two groups of methods that provide partial and complete replacement of petroleum fuel. In case of partial replacement, methanol is mixed with fuel in the amount of 10-40%.

Ethanol is more effective as a fuel additive than methanol, as it dissolves better in hydrocarbons and is less hygroscopic. Gasohol, a mixture of gasoline with 10-20% ethanol, is widely used. In general, ethanol is of particular interest as a fuel additive in certain countries rich in plant resources.

Bioethanol is an alternative type of fuel for powering internal combustion engines, which has an increased environmental friendliness class. A derivative of plant components and agricultural crops, bioethanol demonstrates good performance as an economical fuel for cars, but it also has disadvantages [4].

One of the features of the development of the modern world is the increased attention of the world community to the problems of efficient use of energy resources, the introduction of energy saving technologies and the search for renewable energy sources [4].

Biofuels occupy a special place in the structure of renewable energy sources [4]. In the system of classifying biofuel components by origin, the first generation includes alcohols produced

from food or feed raw materials: sugar cane, sugar beets and some other crops. According to its physicochemical properties, bioethanol meets the conditions for use as a gasoline substitute. It can be used in its pure form (grade E100) [4].

Bioethanol as a fuel has both significant advantages and significant disadvantages. The main advantages of biofuel relate primarily to environmental indicators [5-8].

Bioethanol is a non-toxic fuel that is completely soluble in water. When it burns, no compounds hazardous to the environment or human health are formed. Adding bioethanol to gasoline can reduce harmful emissions by up to 30% or more. In addition, bioethanol is produced from natural, renewable raw materials. It is often a by-product of non-waste production of other types of products [5].

In addition, due to its high octane number, the use of bioethanol can improve some characteristics of an internal combustion engine. Including its efficiency increases [5-8].

Thus, based on the study, it is shown that mixtures of solutions from 5 % to 8% can be used as diesel fuel under given climatic conditions.

Comparative engine traction characteristics when operating on standard and bioethanol-containing fuels showed that when using a mixture, power and thrust increase in force by 6...8%, and specific fuel consumption decreases by 6...7% at the same actual speed. This is due to the improvement of the combustion process when oxygen is dissolved in bioethanol, which indirectly proves a reduction in exhaust gases.

Wear details of the CPG when operating on biofuel depend on the acceleration and load modes. Thus, the average wear rate at idle speed is 6.2...9.9 times less than at maximum load. At the maximum speed mode and load, the concentration of iron (Fe) in the oil composition of an engine running on standard fuel increased from $1.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ to $7.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ g/hour, which is 8-12% more than at work on conventional fuel.

The wear of the upper compression ring over 400 hours of operation was 0.255–0.470 g, i.e. 4–7% less than when the engine was running on standard fuel.